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FORMULATION OF LIPOSOMES CONTAINING EXTRACT OF *CYNODON DACTOLON* Linn. BY 3² FACTORIAL DESIGN

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ABSTRACT

Objective: The objective of the present study was to formulate and evaluate liposomes loaded with extract of *Cynodon dactylon linn*. **Methods:** Liposomes containing extract of *Cynodon dactylon linn* were made by thin layer film hydration method. Soya lecithin and cholesterol were used to make multilamellar vesicles. Nine batches of liposomes were prepared based on the different weight ratio of Soya lecithin and cholesterol. Scanning Camera microscopy, IR, Drug entrapment, Drug release, Diffusion study, Stability study were conducted. **Results:** The prepared liposomes were evaluated by particle size analysis, entrapment efficiency, release study and stability study. Particle sizes were determined from the scanning Camera microscopy (SCM) photographs. It showed that F2, F5 and F8 batches had a good release results and smaller liposomes while F1, F3, F4, F6, F7 and F9 shows a poor release result with a mean at 269 μ m. The percentage entrapment efficiency was found to be 76.13, 83.78, 73.44, 79.81, 86.19, 81.43, 74.32, 83.79, and 71.54 % respectively. The satisfactory batches F2, F5, and F8 was packed in containers and stored at 4°C temperature for one month. At the end of one month, the samples were analyzed for their physical properties, drug entrapment and in vitro release profile. The percentage release was found to be 77.4, 79.24, and 74.9% after 5 hrs. **Conclusion:** The formulation of Liposomes containing extract of *Cynodon dactylon* was carried out. The batches F1 to F9 were evaluated for Scanning camera microscopy, drug entrapment, drug release, diffusion study and stability study, the results are shows, The F2, F5, and F8 batches showed most promising results compared to other batches. No significant change was found during one month's stability study of final batches.

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INTRODUCTION^{1, 2, 3}

Liposome has become an essential therapeutic tool most notably in drug delivery and targeting. Structurally, liposomes are concentric bilayered vesicles in which an aqueous volume is enclosed by a membranous lipid bilayer mainly composed of natural or synthetic phospholipids. Liposomes are formed when thin lipid films or lipid cakes are hydrated and stacks of lipid crystalline bilayers become fluid and swell. The hydrated lipid sheets get detached during agitation and self-close to form large, multilamellar vesicles (MLVs), which prevent interaction of water with the hydrocarbon core of the bilayer at the edges. Liposomal drug delivery system is very useful for delivery of various anticancer, antifungal, topical, antibacterial, ocular and antiviral drugs.¹

The processes of wound healing involve a variety of biological responses, such as an acute inflammation, cellular proliferation and a contraction of the collagen lattice formed. Appropriate method for healing of wounds is essential for the restoration of damaged tissue anatomical continuity and disturbed functional status of the skin. Research on wound healing agents is one of the developing areas in modern biomedical sciences and many traditional practitioners across the world particularly in countries like India and China have valuable information of many plants for treating wounds and burns.

For this reason, traditional plant based remedies are back and find increasing application as source of direct therapeutic agents. among numerous species of plants growing wild in India, doob ghas, or Durva or taxonomically the *Cynodon dactylon* (L.) Pers. family Poaceae occupies its unique place and key position in medicinal practices and traditional medical (Ayurvedic, Unani, Nepalese, and Chinese) knowledge systems. It contains essential oil triticin 12.4%. The other chemical constituents are glycosides, saponins, tannins, flavonoids, & carbohydrates. It also contains agropyrene, arunodin, furfural, furfural alcohol, β -ionine, 2-(4'-hydroxy phenyl) propionic acid, 2-(3'-methoxy-4'-hydroxy-phenyl) propionic acid, 3-methoxy-4-hydroxy benzoic acid, phytol, β sitosterol-D-glucoside, stigmaterol acetate, phagostimulant phytone (6, 10-14-trimethyl pentadecane-2-one).

The aim of work is to formulate and optimize liposomes containing extract of *Cynodon Dactylon* (L.) Pers. For better its bioavailability. Liposomes are an attractive approach as entrapment of *Cynodon Dactylon* (L.) Pers. in lipid based drug delivery can impart several merits like environmental protection, faster and better penetration across the lipid membrane due to increase flux, and improved bioavailability. Our approach has been directed toward investigating the potential of using liposome formulations as carrier system for *Cynodon Dactylon* (L.) Pers. destined for treatment of Wound healing treatment.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Materials

Soya lecithin, cholesterol, Methanol and Dichloromethane were purchased from local market. The extraction was carried out by using dried whole plant of *Cynodon dactylon* (L.) Pers. In hydroalcohol solution (ethanol: water, 70: 30). All the chemicals and reagents were used were of analytical grade.

Collection of plant material

The whole plant of *Cynodon dactylon* (L.) Pers. was collected from the Botanical garden of College Of Pharmacy, Solapur, Dist. Solapur, Maharashtra, India in the months of August to November, cleaned and dried at room temperature in shade and away from direct sunlight.

Authentication of plant

The plant was authenticated at Department of Botany, Walchand College of Arts and Science, Solapur, Maharashtra by comparing morphological features of the collected specimen with a sample voucher of specimen of plant deposited as reference (Reg. MN-77).

Preparation of extract⁵

The whole plant of *Cynodon dactylon* (L.) Pers. was collected and dried in the shade and then pulverized in a grinder. The material was passed through 120 meshes to remove fine powders and coarse powder was used for extraction by Soxhlet extraction using hydroalcoholic solvent (70:30% ratios). The extracted drug was subjected to FT-IR spectrophotometric analysis.

Preliminary phytochemical screening⁴

Phytochemical screening was carried out according to standard methods. Extracts shows the presence of carbohydrates, glycosides, flavonoids, saponins, alkaloids, phenolic compounds, tannins, fixed oil, & mucilage. These constituents are present in selected plant *Cynodon dactylon* (L.) Pers.

Preparation of liposome by thin layer film hydration method⁶

A solution of Soya lecithin and cholesterol in a specified weight and dissolved in 5 ml chloroform. The chloroform solution was placed inside a 250 ml round bottom flask and rotated in the same direction. The flask was kept in a thermostatic water bath, and rotated while maintaining a temperature of 30° to 35°C. Rotation was continued till all the chloroform evaporates from the solution and a thin lipid film was deposited on the inner wall of the flask. An aqueous solution of extract (5 ml containing 100 mg drug) was added to the flask and was rotated with the same speed as before for 30 min or until all the lipid was removed from the wall of the flask. The suspension was allowed to stand for a period of 15 min on water bath at 30°C temperature for complete hydration.

Then, the suspension was taken into a bath type sonicator and sonicated for 30 min. Separation of non-entrapped drug was carried out by centrifugation at 3500 rpm for 40 min. The liposomal suspension was cooled by placing the test tubes in ice-cold water prior to centrifugation. Then liposome was stored at 4°C.

Table 1: Formulation of Liposomes.

Batches Ingredients	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8	F9
Drug	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100
Cholesterol	150	100	50	150	100	50	150	100	50
Soya lecithin	50	100	150	50	100	150	50	100	150
Methanol	02	02	02	02	02	02	02	02	02
Dichloromethane	08	08	08	08	08	08	08	08	08
Buffer	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10
RPM	20000	20000	20000	22000	22000	22000	24000	24000	20000

EVALUATION OF LIPOSOMES

Optical microscopy⁷

One drop of the Liposomal formulation was homogeneously spread onto a glass slide and left to dry overnight. The samples were observed under a Scanning Camera microscope. Photographs were taken at 100X magnifications wherever necessary.

Measurement of particle size⁷

Particle size analysis was done by Beckman Coulter size analyzer.

Drug entrapment efficiency⁶

The drug entrapment efficiency was calculated using the total drug content of liposome dispersion and un-entrapped drug content of the dispersion. The total drug content of the dispersion is determined estimating total drug entrapped and un-entrapped. 5 ml of liposome dispersion was taken in a volumetric flask. The dispersion was subjected to sonication in bath sonicator for 30 minutes. Then the mixture was filtered and estimated after suitable dilution at 269 nm wavelengths by using UV Visible Spectrophotometer. For the free unentrapped drug, 5 ml of the liposome dispersion subjected to centrifugation at 5000 rpm using centrifuge for 40 min at 50°C. The supernatant clear solution was collected separately and the free drug present in the supernatant was analyzed after suitable dilution at 269 nm wavelength by using UV Visible Spectrophotometer to calculate the entrapment efficiency.

In vitro drug release study⁷

5 ml of concentrated liposomal suspension was taken in a test tube of opening diameter of 20 mm. The open end was covered with a semi-permeable dialysis membrane (Himedia Laboratories Pvt. Ltd.) and tied with a thread. The test tube was inverted and placed over the surface of 100 ml water present in a 250 ml beaker in such a way that the membrane just touched the water surface. The test tube was secured by a clamp fixed with a stand. The water in the beaker was stirred with a magnetic stirrer so that no vortex could form in the beaker. The temperature was maintained at 37°C. The drug released from the liposomes permeates across the membrane and enters into the receptor chamber medium. Aliquots of 3 ml were taken out from the receptor chamber medium maintaining sink condition, suitably diluted, and the absorbance was taken by UV-spectrophotometer at 269 nm against a blank of fresh medium.

Stability Study

Many physicochemical parameters are investigated as major reasons for liposome instability. Oxidation and hydrolysis are the main reasons for chemical instability, as they occur in phospholipid unsaturated chains. Stored at 4°C temperatures for One month and light preservation can avoid such reactions. Proper entrapment, pH adjustment, temperature, ionic interaction and application of cholesterol in bilayer structure can successfully cause liposome stability. In this study, liposomes were stored at 4°C temperature for One month.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Table 2: Avg. Globule size, Drug entrapment and In Vitro study.

Batches	Avg. Globule Size (um)	% Entrapment	In vitro drug release study (5 Hrs.)
F1	13.66	76.13	65.62
F2	13.38	83.78	80.8
F3	12.45	73.44	63.9
F4	11.75	79.81	68.2
F5	12.01	86.19	81.59
F6	10.54	81.43	72.62
F7	10.85	74.32	64.79
F8	9.97	83.79	78.97
F9	9.54	71.54	68.66

IR Spectral analysis

Fig. 1: FTIR spectrum of extract.

Fig. 2: % Drug Entrapment.

Measurement of particle size

Particle size analysis was done by Beckman Coulter size analyzer. Fig. 3 to 5 depicts the particle size distribution of F2, F5 and F8 batches. Particle size analysis depict that the liposomes were ranging 190.6, 212.9 and 181.6 nm respectively. The Liposomes prepared with Soya lecithin and Cholesterol shows heterogeneous distribution and shows very irregular pattern except other batches which shows smaller particle size as compared the other batches.

The batches F2, F5 and F8 shows smaller particle size of 190.6, 212.9 and 181.6 nm respectively and having polydispersity index (PDI) of 0.112, 0.114 and 0.187 respectively and diffusion constant $2.588e^{-008}$, $2.316e^{-008}$ and $2.716e^{-008}$ cm²/sec. which shows in following fig. 3, 4 and 5 respectively.

Fig. 3: particle size analysis of F2.

Fig. 4: particle size analysis of F5 batch.

Fig. 5: particle size analysis of F8 batch.

In vitro drug release study

The drug release pattern of all liposome formulations containing extract was shown Table no 3. From the graph, it was seen that the drug release of F2, F5, and F8 batches was fastest and good release. % release at 30 min show that the middle level of cholesterol to Soya lecithin concentration ration demonstrated higher release compared to the other two extremities.

Table 3: Results of *in vitro* drug release study.

Time	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8	F9
30	13.85	19.01	16.53	12.56	19.33	10.94	9.87	20.4	12.02
60	20.39	22.48	22.2	15.41	26.36	15.36	13.18	24.24	22.27
90	24.32	32.06	28.54	22.74	35.73	22.58	21.09	32.47	28.3
120	32.11	43.09	33.77	29.31	45.58	33.36	28.15	40.93	34.28
180	43.88	53.67	44.61	38.31	63.86	47.53	40.78	56.07	43.21
240	56.52	63.67	53.71	53.69	70.5	58.56	48.39	65.17	48.93
300	65.62	80.8	63.9	68.2	81.59	72.02	64.79	78.97	68.66
Best Fit Model	Hixon Crowell	Hixon Crowell	Peppas	Zero Order	1st Order	Hixon Crowell	Zero Order	Hixon Crowell	Peppas

Figure 6: Drug release profiles of prepared batches.

Figure 7: Surface plot for % release at 30 min.

Stability Study

The satisfactory formulation was packed in the tube and stored at 4-8°C temperature for one month. At the end of one month, the samples were analyzed for their physical property, drug entrapment and in vitro release study. The % entrapment efficiency was found 81.12, 84.54, and 79.2 and % release was found 77.4, 79.24, and 74.9% after 5 hrs. So there was no significant change found in one-month stability.

Figure 8: % Release Before and After Stability.

Figure 9: % Drug Entrapment Before and After Stability.

CONCLUSION

This project was performed for aiming as the activity of *Cynodon dactylon (L.) Pers.* extract is a model drug by attempting topical drug delivery in the form of a liposome. After the formulation of liposomes, they were evaluated to estimate their particle size analysis, entrapment efficiency, release study and stability testing. The F2, F5, and F8 batches showed most promising results compared to other batches.

Though, long-term stability study and Formulation of liposomal gel or other topical formulation for wound healing activity, for future development of this formulation.

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Table 4: List of Abbreviations.

Sr. No.	Abbreviations	Full form
1	IR	Infra red
2	Hrs	Hours
3	MLVs	Multilamellar vesicles
4	ml	Milliliter
5	Mg	Microgram
6	Min	Minutes
7	Rpm	Rotation per minute
8	Nm	Nanometer
9	Uv	Ultra violet – visible spectrophotometer

Conflict of interest:

The corresponding authors have no conflict of interest.

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